

Believed Causes of Illness Among Sugbu-Anuns

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Abstract

Though medical and scientific imperial concepts are embraced among Sugbu-anuns, the traditional causes of illness are still evident. This showed the bipolarity of Sugbu-anun archetype of health where the modern and traditional concepts intertwine with no noticeable demarcation. Utilizing ethnography, the researcher analyzed the believed causes of illness. Multiple unstructured interviews were conducted and were confirmed through participatory observation. Fifty key informants were sampled and provided thematic data saturations. The generic beliefs were observed to be rooted in animism, which demonstrates how traceable historical roots embed in modern lifeway. It is a belief system that attributed illnesses to elemental, ancestral or spiritual interference. These included: (1) "gida-ut or gi-usik"; (2) "gibarang"; (3) "buyag"; (4) "gihangup"; and (6) "gabâ". Personal and social causes were also observed. These are helpful data for nurses' decisions and actions in the provision of culture-based nursing care.

Keyword: Ethnography, Sugbu-anuns, Illness, Culture

Introduction

McBride (nd) in her module cited literature written by Anderson (1983), McBride, et al., (1996), and Orque (1983) presenting the principle of balance or "timbang" as a key indigenous health concept among Filipinos. This includes a complex set of fundamental principles that range from "hot" and "cold" beliefs concerning humoral balances in the body, food and dietary balances. These include: (1) rapid shifts from hot to cold that leads to illness; (2) warm environment is essential to maintain optimal health; (3) cold drinks or cooling foods should be avoided in the morning; (4) an overheated body (as in childbirth or fever) is vulnerable and heated body or muscles can get "shocked" when cooled suddenly; (5) a layer of fat (being stout) is preferred to maintain "warmth" and protect vital energy; (6) heat and cooling relate to quality and balance of "hangin" (air) in the body; and (7) sudden changes in weather patterns, cool breezes or exposure in evening hours to low temperature, presence of hot sun immediately after a lengthy rain, vapors rising from the soil all may upset the body balance by simply blowing on the body surface.

Medical and paramedical researchers are not so interested in documenting the believed causes of illness among Sugbu-anuns. There are only few literature and studies written by health professionals with regards to this cultural health belief system. There is a need to textually document these viewpoints for health professionals to utilize as reference when drafting a culturally sensitive plan of care.

Theoretical Framework

Acknowledgment to the importance of cultural health views has led to the development of models for inquiry into patients' beliefs about their illness which includes the Health Belief Model (Becker, 1974) and the Explanatory Model (Kleinman, 1980, 1988a&b). As nurse advocates, it is vital to recognize clients' understanding with regards to their health belief system (believed causes of illness). An understanding to this conception is important for nurses since they utilize different frameworks in defining what is care and what is nursing. Because of these differences, misunderstanding in the part of the patient, nurses and even other health care professionals may occur.

As cited by McBride (nd), among Sugbu-anuns, health and illness are viewed holistically as an equilibrium model (Miranda, McBride & Spangler, 1999; McBride, et al., 1996; Tompar-Tiu & Sustento-Seneriches, 1995; Tan, 1987; Anderson, 1983) encompassing the mystical, personal and natural causes. Mystical causes are often associated with supernatural beings. Personal causes may be attributed to

social punishment or personal retribution. Natural causes include a range of factors from natural events, excessive stress, incompatible food and drugs, infection, or familial susceptibility.

The Health Belief Model, developed by a group of US Public Health Service Psychologist who wanted to explain why so few people were participating in programs to prevent and detect disease, will be utilized to provide a framework for this study. As one of the first theories of health behavior addressed problem behaviors that evoke health concerns (Croyle, 2005).

The health belief model proposes that a person's health-related behavior depends on the person's perception of four critical areas: (1) the severity of a potential illness; (2) the person's susceptibility to that illness; (3) the benefits of taking a preventive action; and (4) the barriers to taking that action. It is a popular model applied in nursing, especially in issues focusing on the relationship between a person's beliefs and behaviors. Patient compliance is affected by their cultural belief system. Thus, nurses needs to consider the clients' cultural perspective in their plan of care (Marriner & Raile, 2005; Polit & Beck, 2007; Black, Hawks & Keene, 2006; Potter & Perry, 2006; Rosenstoch, 1974; Croyle, 2005).

The challenge of cultural competency is to understand culture and theoretical constructs to help ensure effective care despite differences (Leininger & McFarland, 2005). Cultural competence is obtaining cultural information and then applying that knowledge. In order to understand illness, it is necessary to: (1) obtain cultural, religious, social, and economic information; and (2) discover how a patient and significant people in the patient's life view illness, its significance, and its implications (Helman, 1985a&b). Increased cultural awareness is necessary to provide a framework on how to plan a culturally sensitive nursing care that is free from medical ethnocentrism and cultural blindness (Leininger & McFarland, 2005). Cultural awareness allows the nurse to see the entirety and improves the quality of care provided.

To be culturally competent, the nurse needs to respect and understand personal world views of the patient - keeping away from stereotyping that leads to flawed consumption of scientific knowledge (Cultural Diversity, 2008; Bazron, Dennis & Isaacs, 1989). Cultural competence means to really listen to the patient, to find out and learn about the patient's beliefs of health and illness (Cultural Diversity, 2008; Meyer, 1996).

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to document and analyze the believed causes of illness among Sugbu-anuns.

Method

This study employed maxi-ethnonursing method which applied ethnography in nursing (Polit & Beck, 2004; Leininger, 1985). The information gathered was used to analyze the Sugbu-anuns' point of view, aiming to bring forth meaning and understanding through interpretation of their behavior. Nurse and other expert informants' etic perspective on folk care practices and their own professional knowledge confirmed and supplemented the analysis of data.

The main forms of data collection for this study were semi-structured and unstructured self reports obtained from focused group discussions, formal interviews and informal conversations, and participatory observation with reflection and reconfirmation. Multiple in-depth interviews, which followed a formal semi-structured protocol, captured a range of information. Formal interviews were supplemented with multiple informal sessions. Informal meetings occurred in the study participants' home, in the community and in the folk healers' treatment area. Notes from conversations were recorded immediately. The researcher had between 10 to 20 data points for each key informant. The researcher also considered informant active participators who provided narratives and stories. An interactive process transpired, with the aim of making sense of, and gaining meaning about their belief system. Cross-validation and triangulation by gathering different kinds of data were done with confirmations from community health nurses, other health care professionals, local officials, religious and lay informants.

The Leininger's (1985) four-phase sequence in participant observer's role was followed to guide the researcher and investigating assistants on what to do. The phases of Leininger's observation-participation-reflection enabler include: (1) primary observation and active listening; (2) primary

observation with limited participation; (3) primary participation with continuing observation; and (4) primary reflection and reconfirmation of results of informants (Polit & Beck, 2008).

Sample. The researcher approached potential Sugbu-anun lay informants through the help of trusted individuals, known as "gatekeepers". These participants were: (1) residents of Cebu for at least fifteen years; (2) born and reared in the Province of Cebu; (3) between ages thirty-five to sixty-five years old; and (4) had not lived outside Cebu Province.

The researcher used the "big net" approach, mingled and conversed with as many members of the community. Fifty informants were purposively identified from the pool of potential informants. Although there were fifty, ten key informants were selected purposively, guided by the ethnographer's judgments.

Consent. An informed consent form was developed in English with Bisayan translation. The participants were asked to read the consent form and affix their signature. The consent specifically gave permission to audio-visually record or audiotape all transpired sessions. Two research assistants witnessed all consents.

Instruments. The main instrument of the study was the researcher himself. The concept of researcher as instrument was used frequently to describe the significant role ethnographers play in analyzing and interpreting a culture (Polit & Beck, 2004).

To facilitate the researcher in gathering data, a well thought-out interview schedule was utilized. However, the data gathered was not only limited to what was inquired in the interview schedule. The researcher made use of field notes where observations, reports, life stories and informal conversations were transcribed. Observations, reports, and life stories were very helpful in demonstrating actual events.

Fieldwork. When approval from the research committee of the University of the Visayas was obtained, informants were recruited. They were asked to talk and to describe their thoughts about the believed causes of illness among Sugbu-anuns. The researcher accomplished field notes to document the observation, participation and reflection.

Data Analysis. The data analysis based from Leininger's (1991 as cited by Polit & Beck 2008) four phases of analysis for ethnographic qualitative data was utilized. The first phase necessitated description of documented raw data from interviews, participatory observation, reflections and diaries. This supported and facilitated a number of tasks that assist, organize and manage the accumulation of narrative data. Audiotapes, videotapes and field notes were transcribed in verbatim. The researcher verified that transcriptions were precise which authentically reflect the entirety of the sessions. The second phase consisted of the identification of descriptions of the Sugbu-anun culture-based health care practices. Category schemes or thematic guides were developed to manage the data. The third phase entailed discovery and formulation of recurring patterns of Sugbu-anun culture-based health care practices and an analysis of the context in which they occurred. The data were examined in their entirety and coded for correspondence to different categories to assist the researcher in accessing its parts without repeatedly rereading the accumulated documents. The last phase involved abstracting major themes, presentation of findings and drafting of major constructs of the Sugbu-anun culture-based health care practices with the aid of documents from the different culture care models, medical models and ethnographic books.

Results and Discussion: Believed Causes of Illness

Though local folks in the rural and urban areas believed in the genetic, social, psychologic and biologic and causes of illness, traditional causes of illness were also being identified. However, rural Sugbu-anuns believed more on the spiritual side as the cause of illness than the professional medical concepts. These shared traditional causes of illness believed by both rural and urban Sugbu-anuns included: (1) "gida-ut or gi-usik", rawly translated as a sorcery which causes illness without the aid of dolls; (2) "gibarang", rawly translated as a sorcery which causes illness with the aid of dolls; (3) "buyag", an illness caused by "ingkantu u dili ingunatû" (these are environmental spirits, forest spirits or elves; (4) "gihangup" an illness associated with the spirits of ancestors; (5) doing inappropriate behavior; (6) "gabâ", local term for a karma-like experience that brings illness; (7) "pasmu"; (8) teething and pregnancy; and (9) hereditary.

Mystical Causes (Animism)

Mystical causes were attributed to magic, sorcery, ancestral spirits and elemental spirits. These practices presented the collective concept of the "I" among Sugbu-anuns which is not only extended to the living, but also to the immaterial: the dead and the non human form.

These practices were remnants of Sri-Vijayan and Majapahit Indian culture (Abellana, nd; Jainal, 2003). According to Paul Stange (nd), animism remains unspoken; in mystical philosophy it is obviously observed in cultural practice.

"Gida-ut, Gi-usik and Gibarang". Rural and urban Sugbu-anuns shared the same concepts for "gida-ut or gi-usik" and "gibarang". It is defined by Mascuñana and Mascuñana (2004) as any malign magic or sorcery. This allows one to inflict harm to someone who had done something wrong. It could cause the health of the person to deteriorate. When a person who envied or had hatred to an individual seeks services from a Tambalan, that person would ask the Tambalan to make the other person's health miserable. It was believed that when health deteriorates, all aspects of his life would also depreciate. The person could no longer function well, thus pulling off success, wealth and good status. "Gibarang" on the other hand had similarities to this concept. However in "barang", dolls were used as a medium to inflict harm, pain and physical suffering.

The "mangungusik" possessed supernatural powers that would visibly harm the victim's body, usually causing the stomach to distend during high tide and reduce in size during low tide. One resident shared the experience she had with her brother who had experienced this phenomenon. She said that one time her brother pleaded for an ambulance because he could hardly breathe due to over distention of the abdomen. They were on their way to the hospital that the abdomen reduced its size. Her brother then jokedly said, "isuruy nalang ku" (roughly translated as bring to a leisurely ride). However, it was never treated and caused the death of his brother. He was diagnosed with liver cirrhosis.

The "mamamarang" used a technique of sticking nails or needles in a wooden doll causing physical harm to the body. Any part of the body of a person, usually hair, would be attached to the doll. It was believed that when this happened, the part of the doll's body would represent the body part of the victim. For example, if a needle would be pricked in the head, then the victim would experience an unbearable discomfort in the head. This was similar to the reports of Perez (1999) and what was reported in Wikipedia (2010a), wherein "gida-ut" or "gibarang" was defined as the use of voodoo like activity to conjure up a spell, which was recited while piercing the body of a ragdoll, representing the person who is supposed to have the sickness.

Looking at it as a social construct, such conception is not completely bad after all; it provided a framework for social consciousness of not hurting others. Social vengeance of "gida-ut or gi-usik" and "gibarang" allows the person to be fearful not to hurt anyone: to avoid being subjected to such.

"Buyag". In the rural area, it was observed that the concept of "buyag" was more general than those presented among the urban Sugbu-anuns. In the rural area, some major categories of ailments were blamed on the "dili ingun natû" (roughly translated as not like us). These environment spirits were normally impartial towards humans. If they were offended or annoyed, they would retaliate by making the offenders get sick which locals in the area termed "nabuyagan sa dili ingun natû" ("buyag" caused by environmental spirits). Since they were imperceptible, it would be very difficult to avoid them. The "nabuyagan sa la ug dila" ("buyag" of the poisonous tongue) would cause sickness unintentionally by a person's compliment. Although at times this could be deliberately done by an enemy. A person who was complimented should immediately utter the words "pwira buyag" (drive away the "buyag").

"Gihangup". Rural and urban Sugbu-anuns shared the same concepts of "gihangup". "Gihangup" was a sickness associated with the souls of one's deceased ancestors, who might punish their living descendants for misbehavior or neglect. Locals call it "gipahimunduman" (letting one remember). This was a way for these ancestral spirits to ask help from their relative. The relative would then offer a mass for their deceased loved ones called "pamisa". They could also give "rigalu" (offering gifts in a form of food usually the favorite of their deceased loved ones).

"Buyag" and "gihangup" reminds Sugbu-anuns to respect and have a good relationship with the dead and elemental spirits. This concept demonstrated the importance of the "others" to the "I".

Personalistic Causes

Personalistic causes further demonstrate the importance of the collective "I" system among Sugbu-anuns:

"Gabâ". When a person had done inappropriate behavior, this person could be ill. The illness was believed to be God-given or inflicted by the ancestral spirits. On the contrary, "Gabâ" was the concept of a non-earthly (human) and non-heavenly (God or ancestral spirit) instinctive unconscious personal retribution among Sugbu-anuns. This was similar to the definition provided by Wikipedia (2010b). This personal punishment was usually in a form of "nakunsinsya" (conscience) or "nasakit" (ill). Feeling ill might be the result of the unconscious over thinking of the performed unacceptable deeds. It was similar but not the same with the Hinduistic concept of karma. Nowadays, Sugbu-anuns associate this concept with the Christian teachings. This was the influence of religion to this more ancient conviction: the Hinduistic-animistic concept was Christianized to fit in the recent religious credence.

Sugbu-anuns had popular statements which summarized the principles of "gabâ": (1) "Ang gabâ pwidi adtu mutaput sa imuhang minahal"(it might possibly occur to the loved ones of the violator (2) "Ang gabâ dili magsaba" (it might arrive without warning); (3) "Ang gabâ dili parihang sa sili nga muhalang dayun" (its effect was non immediate); (4) "Ayaw yagâ-yaga-i ang sagradung mga butang kay makagabâ" (personal retribution might be caused by sacred items); (5) "ang impurtanting mga butang makagabâ" (important things might cause personal retribution); (6)"ang tanan na adunay kinabuhi makagabâ" (anything with life might cause personal retribution); and (7) ang pagka-un makagabâ (food might cause personal retribution); and (8) "ang mga katiguwangan labaw na makagabâ" (elders highly cause the personal retribution). Some of these proverbs were presented in the manuscripts of Guiraldo Fernandez (2004), Lilian Garcia (1976) and Luz Lomoljo (1994).

The rationale behind this phenomenon could be traced in the collective "I" system. "I in Us", as the core of the Sugbu-anun personality, identified personhood as an ecology-friendly, systematic orientation (De Guia, 2005; 2008). She added that this signaled the "I" as one with humanity", and I connected with creation and/or environment. She stressed that this was a basic quality of life rooted from an animist framework, an extension of the Sugbu-anuns ancestral memories.

An alternative explanation was anchored in bio-psychological concepts. The physical malady experienced might be the conversion of cognitive tensions (feeling shame or feeling bad when something not acceptable was done) manifested in physical symptoms. Conversion or somatization, as a defense mechanism, is defined as the conversion of psychic derivatives into bodily symptoms and tending to react with somatic manifestations, rather than psychic manifestations (Kaplan & Sadock, 1998).

Naturalistic Causes

"Pasmu". "Pasmu" was based in the concept of "init" (heat) and "bugnaw" (cold) and how the blending of these two can result in illnesses. According to McBride (2001), Basilgo (1994) and Licauco (1982), "tu-ub" or "panghimasmu" was a steaming ritual and a faith healing practice to achieve "timbang". "Pasmu" can be experienced when there is a rapid shift from hot to cold. It was believed that a warm environment is essential to maintain optimal health and when disturbed creates the imbalance. Still relating to this concept, cold drinks and foods were also avoided especially in the morning (Anderson, 1983; McBride, et al., 1996; Orque, 1983).

Teething and Pregnancy. Another alternative believed source of illness in both rural and urban areas were teething and pregnancy. It was believed that when teething occurs, the individual will experience fever, pain, and other gastric and respiratory discomforts.

Signs of pregnancy and other pregnancy related discomforts, as claimed by the medical model, were interpreted by the folk people to be illnesses brought about by pregnancy. However, some believed that these manifestations were related to the process of pregnancy. These were: (1) nausea and vomiting; (2) swelling of the lower and upper extremities; (3) increased blood pressure; (4) diabetes (gestational induced); (5) back pain; and (6) increased frequency of urination; (7) fatigue; (8) dental and oral problems; and (9) changes in the skin.

Heredity. Some Sugbu-anuns believed that some diseases were inherited. Folks would say "kaliwat man gud nila" (It is hereditary).

Researcher's Reflection

Clients might have beliefs that attribute illness to a spiritual, animistic, personalistic, or naturalistic disruption. Thematically, these beliefs are linked to the concept of the collective "I" (De Guia, 2005; 2008) among Sugbu-anuns which demonstrates the importance of the society in the individual system. This is being manifested in their health-illness construct which should be considered in the nurse's care plan.

Healing for these clients might appear to be unrelated to current treatment practices. The nurse needs to assess the client's beliefs and, if possible, include in planning some aspects of healing that were part of the client's belief system (Kozier, 2004).

Nurses and health care providers needs to: (1) learn to ask questions sensitively; (2) show respect for different cultural beliefs; (3) listen to patients carefully; (4) value differences; and (5) adapt to cultural differences. The main source of problems is the lack of cultural understanding and tolerance which leads to misunderstanding in the part of the nurse and the patient.

Conclusion

Traditional believed causes of illness among Sugbu-anuns were rooted in mystical, personalistic and naturalistic causes. Mystical causes were deeply entrenched to the concept of "timbang" or balance. Personal causes are intensely embedded with the Subu-anons attachment to the family and community.

Utilizing concepts in Culture Care Theory and Health Belief Model, nurses and health care providers needs to assess and respect different cultural belief system in order to arrive in a culturally congruent care plans. Culturally related problems may arise when there is lack of understanding and tolerance from nurses caring for patients with traditional belief system.

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